

**EVIDENCE INFORMED DECISION,
DESIGN, COMMISSIONING AND
DELIVERY**

POPULATION DATA

1

Helps us understand who the greenspace is for, their needs and how it's changing over time: age distribution, ethnic diversity, health indicators, socioeconomic status, behaviours.

LIVED EXPERIENCE

4

Feedback from residents, community consultations, stories from park users. Community champions, park rangers, Get Doncaster Moving.

ACADEMIC RESEARCH

2

Studies that highlight good practice to guide planning delivery, the health benefits of green spaces, biodiversity impact. Safer Parks Guidance and other literature.

ORGANISATIONAL DATA

5

Data generated by LA. Budget allocations and financial constraints, incident reports (e.g., safety issues in existing parks), strategic priorities (e.g., climate targets, biodiversity goals, physical inactivity statistics).

PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE

3

Insights from landscape architects, urban planners, and maintenance teams

IMPACT MEASUREMENT DATA

6

Evaluation of services or interventions and impact measurements. Iteratively feed into decisions, practice and design.

City of
Doncaster
Council

GET
DONCASTER
MOVING

NIHR

Health Determinants
Research Collaboration
Doncaster